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High performance flexible piezoresistive sensor with graft-copolymerized composites

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Example from Research group –flexible pressure sensor

Pressure tracing

X. Wang, et al., Adv. Mater., 2015, 27, 2324–2331.

Shape detection

Nela, L., et al. (2018). Nano letters 18(3): 2054-2059.

Mechanical arm

Oh, H., et al., Sci. Adv., 2020, 6(46): eabd7795.

E-skin

F. Zhang, et al., Nat. Commun., 2015, 6, 8356.

Avata

Virtual reality(VR)

Augmented Reality(AR)

Meta

The pressure sensing mechanism and application

Pressure sensing mechanism:

piezoresistive

capacitive

piezoelectric

triboelectric

Piezoresistive advantages:

High sensitivity (Medical & Health)

Low power dissipation

High resolution

... ..

E-skin

Medical

Intelligent limb

Traditional piezoresistive sensor

Flexible and thin film piezoresistive sensor

Curved surface or narrow space (such as **inside eye**), special shape materials and devices are required!

Three most widely reported piezoresistive materials

2D, sensitive, narrow sensitive regime

2-2 composite, sensitive, Young's modulus mismatch

(0,1,2)-3 composite, sensitive regime and reliability

Easy to deform fastly, easy to achieve high sensitivity

The problems of widely reported pressure sensor

① Slow stabilization

slow

(1) The relaxation is obvious, hard to get stabilized

② Poor repeatability

drift and hysteresis

(2) Creep or even plastic deformation

③ Poor stability

delamination

(3) Young's modulus mismatch

④ Low sensitivity

insensitive

(4) Trade off between sensitivity and stability

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Relaxation time

Relaxation: **Relaxation time: the speed of relaxation process**

Prolong the relaxation time

Whether the process can be regarded as a relaxation process depends on observation time

- 1) Relaxation time $\tau \ll$ observation time — transient processes ;
- 2) Relaxation time $\tau \approx$ observation time — relaxation processes ;
- 3) Relaxation time $\tau \gg$ observation time — relaxation is hard to occur ;

How to avoid relaxation of segments :

- | | |
|-----------------------------|---------------|
| 1) energy | 2) space; |
| (determined by temperature) | (free volume) |

Methods: Principles of relaxation and creep

Working temperature < T_g

Glass Transition (T_g)

- ❖ Segment movement
- Deformation increases

Viscous Transition (T_f)

- ❖ Chain movement begins
- ❖ Flow

Conditions of movement

- ❖ Energy (Temperature)
- ❖ Space (Free volume)

Iso-free-volume

Chain movement resistance

Glass state

Glass transition temp. (T_g)

**The polymer with higher T_g , higher modulus,
longer relaxation time and higher stability could be achieved.**

But, lower sensitivity and plastic deformation

How to enhance sensitivity on the basis of stability???

Typical creep curve

When compressed, three kinds of deformation might occur simultaneously:

- Elastic ϵ_1 : rebound immediately;
- Viscoelastic ϵ_2 : entropy derived,
- Plastic ϵ_3 : permanent and irreversible

The total deformation:

$$\epsilon = \epsilon_1 + \epsilon_2 + \epsilon_3 = \sigma_0 \left[\frac{1}{E_1} + \frac{1}{E_2} (1 - e^{-t/\tau}) + \frac{t}{\eta_3} \right]$$

Design a piezoresistive composite with high Young's modulus, without ϵ_3 or even ϵ_2 ,

Fast response, high stability, how about high sensitivity?

The design of high Tg graft-copolymerized composite

1. Stability: extend relaxation time

1). matrix: high Tg₁

2). semiconductor: high Tg₂

2. Sensitivity: increase the active site

large specific surface area matrix+ grating nanostructure

The key: strong interfacial bonding, thermodynamic compatibility and form high Tg composite

$$\frac{1}{T_g} = \frac{1}{\omega_1 + B\omega_2} \left[\frac{\omega_1}{T_{g1}} + \frac{B\omega_2}{T_{g2}} \right]$$

The thermodynamic compatibility of the copolymer, one Tg.

The design of high Tg matrix

TFDB:FDA=8:2
radius of gyration: 23.15 Å

TFDB:FDA=5:5
radius of gyration: 31.83 Å

TFDB:FDA=2:8
radius of gyration: 46.8 Å

Strong interface bonding

Weak interface bonding, shear fracture

W/O HCl

Strong interface bonding, high stress transfer efficiency

W HCl

The design and construction of the pressure sensor

Planar device construction

Tubular device construction
(With shape memory effect)

The key parameters of the pressure sensor

Fast response time < 1.6ms

Stable low drift (<5% in 30 days)

sensitive <100Pa

High dynamic stability:

The decay <2% after 40000 cycles

Sudden infant death syndrome

- I. Occur during sleep – sleep apnea
- II. No clear criterion for the confirmation of possible victims
- III. No effective interventions while asleep

Apnea monitor

Apnea monitor

Apnea belt

medlineplus.gov

- ❖ Newborns
- ❖ Especially premature

❖ **Wired** ❖ **Expensive for home care**

Wearable devices suitable for infants

- Respiration monitoring
- Instant notification

Flexible pressure sensor based on PLA-PANI

To be submitted

Flexible pressure sensor based on PLA-PANI

Flexible pressure sensor based on PLA-PANI

Flexible pressure sensor array based on PANI-PANI

Visualization of Pressure Distribution

8 x 8 array :

- 2 fps
- Detection limit < 100 Pa

In preparation

Flexible pressure sensor array

Inside of the tube

Realtime display of Pressure data

Water pressure detecting application

- Water should be poured into kidney
- High pressure will cause damage
- The pressure cannot be detectable in-situ

Soft ureteroscope to measure water pressure

Flexible pressure sensor based on PES/TPU-PPy

In preparation

Flexible pressure sensor based on PES/TPU-PPy

In preparation

Summary

- ❑ Decreased **signal drift and hysteresis with high Tg matrix**
- ❑ Improved the **stability using strong interfacial bonding** (MD simulation and experiments)
- ❑ Prohibited the movement of fibers via **nanostructure interlocking** enabled by PAMD nanostructured electrodes
- ❑ Developed a **wireless respiration monitoring system**

Acknowledgement

Thanks for listening!